

RTBV was, however, detectable in TKM6, Gam Pai 30-12-15, and TN1 throughout the period after its detection. The results indicate that the virus

concentration in Utri Merah and Balimau Putih was reduced over time to below the level of detection and is the reason why past tests done at 3-4 WAI showed low

infection rates of RTBV. The results also suggest that Utri Merah and Balimau

Relationship between phenylalanine ammonialase (PAL) activity and blast (BI) resistance in rice

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We randomly selected seedlings of 30 rice cultivars at the three-leaf stage. They were surface-sterilized in 0.1% HgCl₂ for 5 min at room temperature, and then

Relationship between BI resistance scores and PAL activity in rice seedlings.

Cultivar	Score ^a	PAL activity (OD ₂₃₀ /g fresh wt per h)
Toride 1	0	0.435
Zhaiyeqing 8	1	0.429
Xiangzaoxian 1	1	0.416
IR52	2	0.423
IR62	3	0.431
Sanerai	3	0.423
Jinwan 1	3	0.421
Jinyou 1	3	0.417
Yangdao 2	3	0.416
IR29	3	0.389
Correlation coefficient		-0.4475 ns ^b
Teqing	4	0.420
Zhefu 802	4	0.404
IR58	4	0.400
Erjiufeng	4	0.393
Zaoxian 143	4	0.390
Lunhui 422	4	0.387
6188	4	0.372
M112	5	0.378
77-175	5	0.345
Jinxi 14	6	0.381
Hongyun 33	6	0.381
Jinzaio 6	6	0.363
Erjiuai	6	0.346
73-07	6	0.342
Shenghong 16	7	0.374
22	7	0.359
Guichao 2	8	0.353
Menggudao	9	0.325
Hong 410	9	0.314
LJXTHG	9	0.309
Correlation coefficient		-0.8398*** ^c

^aBased on SES scale of 0-9. ^bNonsignificant at 5% probability level. ^cSignificant at 1% probability level.

rinsed five times in sterile distilled water. Leaves were cut off and crushed by hammering individually in boric acid buffer (pH 8.8), each liter supplemented with 0.5 g polyvinyl pyrrolidone. The mixture was centrifuged three times at 5,000 rpm for 25 min at 4 °C. Then 0.5 ml of the supernatant was mixed in a test tube with 3.5 ml of a reaction mixture that contained 20 mmol L-Phe 2 ml/liter and allowed to rest for 60 min at 30 °C. The absorbance of the mixture at 290 nm was recorded using a UV 120-02-01 model Ultraviolet-spectrophotometer

(Shimadzu Ltd. Co., Japan). The experiment was replicated four times.

The correlation coefficient was nonsignificant at 5% probability level for PAL activity and BI resistance in rice cultivars (*Standard evaluation system for rice* [SES] scores of 0-3) on the qualitative scale based on lesion type, but it was significant at 1% probability (scores of 4-9) on the quantitative scale based on the percentage of leaf area affected. This indicates that PAL activity increased as the BI resistance score decreased from 4 to 9 (see table). ■

Efficiency of natural selection for bacterial sheath rot (BSR) in bulked families

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BSR, induced by *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae* Tanii, Miyajima, et Akita, was earlier reported on rice only in the northern part of Hokkaido, Japan. It was discovered in Burundi in 1982. This disease has since been identified in Madagascar and Latin America in rice, sorghum, maize, and wheat. In rice, BSR causes poor panicle exertion, leading to sterility of the nonexserted part of the panicle.

BSR is particularly damaging to modern varieties with the *sd1* gene and partially explains the poor performance of fixed varieties in the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery. We compared Ambalalava, a tall, fixed, variety that is well-adapted to BSR, with two F₃, F₆, F₇, and F₈ bulked populations from 1988 to 1991 at the same site at 1,550 m asl.

The two populations were grown at the site in 1987, but BSR pressure was very low. BSR incidence was measured as the percentage of partially exserted

panicles in a sample of 10 pots with three replications. Severity was estimated by the difference in weight between 25 sampled panicles with and without disease (mean of three replications).

Yield loss is measured by the incidence multiplied by severity of BSR.

1. BSR incidence in Burundi, 1988-91.

2. BSR severity in Burundi, 1988-91.

The fluctuation of incidence on control Ambalalava reflects the year-to-year climatic variation; the lower the temperatures, the higher the incidence (Fig. 1). The incidence on bulk populations was very high and did not change between 1988 and 1989, although yield loss decreased from 55 to 25%, which was the level of the control. Natural selection eliminated the individuals that

showed a high severity in 1988 (Fig. 2).

In 1990, no incidences or losses occurred on Ambalalava. The incidence in the hybrids stayed at the same level as Ambalalava in the preceding year, but with only 4% of the losses (Fig. 1). Incidence increased 10% for the hybrids the following year, resulting in increased losses of 8% for Ambalalava and 22% for the hybrid families.

The differences of scale between the two groups are due to the *sd₁* gene. It has a critical threshold of incidence that leads to losses of 30-40% in modern varieties. Good panicle exertion is needed to lessen BSR losses. We are using IR50, which has the *eui* (elongated uppermost internode) gene, in our breeding program to obtain modern varieties that are more resistant to BSR. ■

IRGC 100139, an accession of *Oryza glaberrima* sensitive to rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV)

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RTSV is a latent virus of rice. About 1,200 rice accessions have been tested at IRRI for RTSV, but none of them were sensitive enough to show distinct symptoms of RTSV infection.

We tested four accessions of *O. glaberrima* for sensitivity to RTSV by

inoculating 7-d-old seedlings with one adult green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant)/plant for 24 h in a test tube. The infected plants showed marked stunting, reduced tillering, and pale green leaves at 3-4 wk after inoculation (see figure). Flowering was delayed and panicles were short with few, small grains. Inoculation infected 80-90% of plants.

IRGC 100139 is the first rice accession of *O. glaberrima* identified at IRRI that consistently showed distinct symptoms when infected with RTSV. IRGC 100139 is also a good virus source. When adult GLH had 3 d access to RTSV-infected IRGC 100139 plants,

more than 80% of the insects transmitted the virus to either TN1 or IRGC 100139. The results indicate that RTSV can be maintained and propagated in IRGC 100139.

At present, RTSV is detected in plants by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay or by latex test. These tests are expensive and are not available in most laboratories in developing countries. The tests could be eliminated by using IRGC 100139 as an indicator plant for RTSV. The accession can be used to monitor RTSV-carrying leafhoppers caught in the field and for survey of RTSV occurrence in regions where no tungro symptoms are visible. ■

Healthy (left) and RTSV-infected (right) *O. glaberrima* plants at 21 d after inoculation.

Resistance to rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) in rice germplasm

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We used the mass screening test to determine resistance to rice tungro disease (RTD) of about 16,000 accessions of the International Rice Germplasm Center (IRGC). We selected 510 accessions that showed resistance to RTD and tested for resistance to rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) using forced inoculation in test tubes and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

Plants were inoculated by confining a 6-d-old seedling with three viruliferous green leafhoppers (GLH) in a test tube for 24 h. Inoculated seedlings were transplanted into pots and grown in a greenhouse. Serological indexing was carried out 30 d after inoculation by taking 10-cm-long pieces from the 2d or

3d youngest leaf of each of the 40 plants/ accession.

When inoculated with rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and RTSV, only one accession showed a RTBV infection rate of less than 10%, while 251 accessions (49%) showed a RTSV infection rate below 10%; 147 accessions (29%) were not infected with RTSV.

We further evaluated 134 accessions with RTSV-infection rate below 10% by inoculating them with RTSV alone to confirm their resistance. Results revealed that 115 accessions (86%) had an RTSV infection rate below 10%. Seventy-six accessions were not infected with RTSV in the two experiments (see table on next page).

These results indicate that many varieties are available to serve as sources of resistance to RTSV. Some accessions that had low RTSV infection rates in both experiments and GLH resistance (resistance score <5) were omitted from the table because they may show RTSV resistance caused by vector resistance. ■